

How to get an A+:

A Recipe and Rubric for the English language classroom

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Abstract

This Treball Final del Masters (TFM) discusses an action research project that took place during the authors' 7-week practicum teaching English as a foreign language at the public adult education center, EOIX. The authors presented a 6-session (12-hour) Didactic Sequence to two 2 class groups of approximately 30 students (A2-B1 level) using the Task-based Language Teaching (TBTL) methodology. The authors detected a need to develop a framework for introducing tasks and genre in the classroom. The project aims to help students that are learning a language based on the TBTL methodology to face classroom tasks with more confidence and provide them with a way to measure their own progress and or success via an innovative framework for introducing tasks into the classroom. The result is a set of practical and adaptable tools that provide students with clearer criteria that empower them to achieve their personal best via a "recipe" for success and invite students to participate in the assessment process which, in turn, allows them to take responsibility for defining their own learning goals.

Revision history

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v2.0	11 May 2018	Initial TFM submission for review.
v3.0	03 June 2018	Addressed Reviewer comments: Added reference to Freixas (2017) and addressed all minor grammatical errors (typos). Updated Table of contents, added Revision history table and updated References, adjusted formatting, accordingly.
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1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives

In Task-based Language Teaching or TBLT, classroom focus shifts from the Teacher to the Student (student-centered) who must perform real-world and meaningful tasks using his or her own language and not simply repeating the language of others. A critical aspect of the TBLT methodology is that “task completion is the priority which means that the assessment is based on the larger (non-linguistic) outcome of the task” (Skehan, 2003).

In environments that employ the TBLT methodology, some students struggle to see their own progress because they do not see the “evidence” of their progress in a form that is familiar to them. Tasks are messier than tests. Students that come from a traditional learning environment may be more accustomed to citing traditional assessment methods such as exercises and exams as proof of their competence in the language; however, exercises and exams are not the focal point of their Task-based learning. In fact, these students from traditional learning environments often see their language learning progress entirely in terms of linguistic features while they are being graded in terms of communicative competencies. This apples to oranges comparison can result in disoriented and frustrated students.

During our 7-week practicum at the public adult language school that we will refer to as EOIX (second level English classroom), we observed first-hand our students’ feelings of disorientation and frustration which they associated with (what they perceived to be) a lack of progress in the course. We also observed their questioning the EOIX methodology because of their inability to understand the TBLT-based syllabus.

The global goals of this Action Research Project or Treball Final del Masters (TFM) are (1) to help students that are learning a language based on the TBLT methodology to face classroom tasks with more confidence and (2) to provide these students with a way to measure their own progress and or success via criteria-based assessment techniques.

Our specific goal is to provide an innovative framework for introducing tasks into the classroom via practical and adaptable tools that:

- Provide students with clearer criteria that empower them to achieve their personal best via a “recipe” for success.
- Invite students to participate in the assessment process which, in turn, allows them to take responsibility for defining their own learning goals.

In addition to helping facilitate student learning, our hope is that this framework and the accompanying tools will:

- Take TBLT methodologies a step further by incorporating best practices in assessment for EOIs following this approach.
- Potentially simplify the assessment work of the teacher.
- Help teachers prepare for the shift to the competency-based curriculum in the Catalan public language schools, the Escoles Oficials d’Idiomes, per the recent BOE-A-2017-15367, 23 December of 2017.

The result of this TFM is a set of tools for EOI teachers and beyond that may be employed in a variety of situations and adapted to a variety of different languages where TBLT methodology is prevalent. We will refer to these tools throughout this paper as (1) the Task Description, (2) the Recipe, (3) the “How to get an A+” or simply A+ Rubric and Checklist and (4) the Reflection-aire.

1.2 Target audience and scope

This document follows the Action Research (AR) approach which consists of a cyclical process that begins with the observation of a problem and proposal for “action” that is monitored for progress toward specific outcomes or objectives. We initially define the problem as the critical incident that we observed during the teaching practicum at the EOIX. Rather than repeatedly characterizing the incident as a problem, we feel it important to point out that what we witnessed was a part of a relatively common occurrence in the foreign language classroom – students (and in this case, adult students) that lack the confidence to produce language. For this reason, we chose this incident as inspiration for designing a “Recipe” or functional breakdown of the genre into unit learning goals as they are attained within a Unit Task and subsequently implementing clearer assessment guidelines via the “How to get an A+” Rubric as a means of improving student confidence and motivation, during our 6-session Didactic Sequence. Throughout the document, we hope the reader will see how we employ the AR approach to understand and improve upon our own teaching practice and the teaching practices of our peers.

This TFM is intended for English language teachers that are interested in improving their assessment processes to better reflect the TBLT methodology and competency-based learning, but that have little time to develop these processes. These same teachers may be considering having students participate directly in the rubric design process but are unclear as to where to begin. Additionally, this TFM is designed to provide an initial direction for teachers that are preparing for the shift to competency-based curriculum in the Catalonia public language schools, *Escoles Oficials d’Idiomes*, per the recent BOE-A-2017-15367, 23 December of 2017. This is the first time the EOI Curriculum will reflect this shift in assessment philosophy which is complementary to the TBLT methodology; the change has already taken place in the secondary school Curriculum. Our hope is that this TFM provides the EOI with an opportunity to more closely align their assessment methods with their methodology which will in turn reflect the competency-based nature of the new Curriculum.

1.3 Critical incident

The objectives of our TFM emerged from a critical incident that we witnessed during the observation phase in one of our second-level English classes (A2-B1 level). The incident was a discussion between the teacher and the class as a whole consisting largely of adults in their 20s to 60s. The incidence took place at the beginning of a Session dedicated to the end of Term Task. The students had already completed the first part of the task in the previous session, and they were convinced that it had not gone well because they had run into technology problems in addition to having run out of time.

In this moment of stress, the students complained individually about various aspects of the course including the pacing and the speed of the teacher’s spoken English, but there

was one complaint that seemed to register with the larger group. The students felt somewhat lost in the course; they didn't understand the unit or course objectives or rather they felt that these objectives were somehow hidden from them. Some even suggested that would be better off following a more traditional course with stricter adherence to a coursebook. For us, the student teachers, it was not too difficult to see the situation from the students' perspective, considering that neither of us had studied a foreign language using the task-based method. And yet, both of us could see evidence that the method was working. Students were expressing these concerns to the teacher *in English*. Moreover, students generally expressed themselves well in English during day to day work as well as one-on-one.

The critical incident let us to ask ourselves the following questions:

1. Why did the students often feel incompetent and unconfident in the classroom and, in particular, on task day?
2. How was it that students could not see that they were learning English?
3. What could we provide that would address these feelings of incompetence and inadequacy?

We will use the rest of this paper to discuss how we addressed these questions during our Didactic Sequence, a 6-session series dedicated to a unit on Technology. At the same time, we will provide hints for improvements upon our initial approaches to address our own shortcomings.

1.4 Theoretical basis

For many of our adult EOIX students, there is a wide chasm between the traditional language learning methodology that they have experienced over the course of their lives and the Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) methodology. In this section, we will examine how to address this chasm as part of the theoretical basis for this TFM. First, we will examine the underpinnings of TBLT in depth and try to understand how its focus on “meaning” over the focus on “forms” of traditional language learning methodologies might influence student perceptions of learning and progress. Next, we will discuss the role of meaningful learning and the Zone of Proximal Development or ZPD (explained below) as they pertain to EOIX task focus on genres. Finally, we will examine a constructivist way forward using rubrics.

In order to understand how different TBLT is from more traditional language learning methodologies, we must observe how TBLT fits within the context of the EOIX. As we have discussed, in the TBLT methodology, teaching sessions revolve around the completion of a task. At the EOIX in particular, the didactic teaching units focus on the completion of a Unit Task which is always based on a specific genre or communicative purpose. As a result, when planning a didactic unit, the teacher first determines the genre of this Unit Task and subsequently analyzes the text typologies and then specific language that is needed to successfully accomplish the Unit Task. Students focus on learning how to deal with the language session by session through activities or sub-tasks that provide scaffolding or intermediary steps toward the Unit Task. The overarching goal throughout the sequence is the focus on meaning - communication - and not on form because “when we learn a language naturalistically, we do so by focusing primarily on what we want to say (i.e., meaning) rather than on how we say it (i.e., form)” (Ellis, 2008). Additionally, these Unit Tasks (and subtasks or activities) usually present a gap (Erlam, 2015) where the learner must deduce

meaning from a text or situation in order to deliver information, give an opinion or take action.

TBLT focuses on learning language by using it, but it also includes, as Long defines it, an emphasis or focus on form which assumes that acquisition occurs best when learners' attention is drawn to language items when they are needed for communication (Long M., 1991). This means that students begin by using the language they already know, while teachers introduce new vocabulary and structures only when they are necessary and in order to complete the task. The end of a task sequence, or in this case during the latter part of a single EOIX session, is usually the best moment to study the specific forms which have been used previously during the session (Richards, J.C. & Rodgers, T.S, 2014). In this way, the learners make sense of the language to which they have just been exposed.

In order to understand the EOIX learner's sense of disorientation, we can contrast more traditional approaches to TBLT as a whole. To begin with, more traditional approaches tend to focus on form rather than forms. The term form (as opposed to forms) is described by Long as traditional language teaching consisting of the presentation and practice of items drawn from a structural syllabus (Long, 1991). When our EOIX adult students previously studied the English language, we can imagine a unit beginning with the teacher (teacher-centered) introducing the adjective as the key language for descriptions. There is no communication, there is no gap. It is the structure of the language that drives the session and the didactic unit. In contrast, TBLT turns language learning (as many of our students know it) on its head. The EOIX teacher selects the genre of the Unit Task (a commercial to sell a new gadget) and then presents communicative activities and sub-tasks that introduce the language that is needed for the text typologies associated with this genre (description, argumentation). After the language required for communication has been introduced, the teacher focuses on eliciting these typologies or forms by having the students (student-centered) reflect on the language forms that were needed for that specific communication. It is the Unit Task (activities or sub-tasks) that drives the session and the didactic unit.

Next, we must consider the primary role of genre in TBLT as it is employed at the EOIX. As we have mentioned, the genre or social communicative function behind the Unit Task drives much of the momentum of the unit. Rasuki points out that teaching genre aims at connecting meaning and form in directly and clearly for learners, and as a consequence they are empowered to formulate their ideas properly and precisely (Rasuki, 2016). That said, while most of these genres may be easily recognizable to adult students (a formal letter of complaint or commercial), some are less familiar (a product pitch presentation or video recipe). Students that have studied via more conventional methodologies often don't recognize the importance of the role of genre in the didactic teaching unit because genre is not explicitly taught at the EOIX. This is particularly important when we consider Vygotsky and the Zone of Proximal Development or ZPD (Vygotsky, 1978). We can define the ZPD as the gap between what is already known by the learner and what is not known yet. The ZPD includes the skills too complicated for a specific learner to be mastered on his or her own, though they can be mastered with proper scaffolding. In order for the ZPD to play its vital role within the foreign language classroom, the students must be conscious of the learning that has already taken place (what they "know") and what they will be able to master with the proper scaffolding (meaning both guidance and encouragement from a

knowledgeable person, usually the foreign language teacher). The point is that for a student to master a new genre, the student must be conscious that he or she, indeed, is learning genre with each didactic unit so that he or she can then compare a previously learned genre with a new genre and build upon that foundation.

We have described several important aspects of the gap between the expectation of EOIX students that largely come from a more traditional learning environment and the TBLT classroom. Now we turn our attention to addressing this gap (or chasm) and defining a way forward. In the sections to follow, we will describe a new framework for introducing Unit Tasks. With this framework, we hope to call explicit attention to some important aspects of the TBLT methodology so as to help students recognize the larger learning process. We do this mainly through constructivist methods that ask the students to breakdown the Unit Task into its principle genre components via “the Recipe” and then to reconstruct and define it based on “what they know” into the “How to get an A+ Rubric” according to their own ZPD. We will also talk about Regular (meaning on a regular basis) Reflection via the Reflection-aire, a survey for taking stock of individual progress throughout the year.

The aim of the Recipe and the A+ Rubric is to help learners to feel more confident coming into the classroom. Explaining the assessment criteria and indicators to learners sets a framework of expectations, guides them through the learning process, and ultimately allows them to assess themselves, therefore allowing students to become more and more autonomous as learners (Esteve & Fernández, 2013). We explicitly define the rubric for our students as a cheat sheet or “*chuleta*” for success, a guide to be referenced throughout the Unit Task process.

This criteria-based assessment, in which teachers provide learners with explicit definitions of knowledge and capacities to be assessed, results in the following additional advantages: First, the reference criteria make a transparent route which guides and points learners into the right direction. Second, assessment tasks begin to approach the communicative necessities of daily life, making them more authentic. Third, task results become easier to understand and interpret, while providing students with useful information at the same time. In fact, criteria-based assessment can help to establish a dialogue between teachers and learners about individual learner progress and the results from different students can be compared, as long as tasks and objectives are the same (Escobar, 2006).

In addition to implementing criteria-based assessment, we suggest regular reflection as a means of surveying student progress over the course of the year. We propose a tool for reflection or Reflection-aire as a means of surveying what was learned during the last unit taught. By answering the survey, the student may self-assess his or her own progress as well as make specific observations about the learning process. Throughout this process, students learn to identify their strengths and their deficits which allows them to subsequently look for tools for improvement.

The overall approach not only benefits students; it may also benefit teachers. The European Commission has proposed a set of eight key competencies for the teaching profession in order to address a gap in current pedagogical training models. The *Agència per a la Qualitat del Sistema Universitari de Catalunya* or AQU is promoting this agenda as a means of establishing a highly qualified teacher cohort (Freixa, 2017).

Our hope is that our tools may be used by teachers to improve fundamental teaching competencies to guarantee a level of quality (Quality Assurance) in the classroom as well as to promote collaborative learning methods (Cooperation and Collaboration).

In summary, we believe that to understand the incidence of the EOIX, it is important to understand the key differences between TBLT and more traditional learning scenarios, and we have taken this into account when determining the appropriate intervention. We believe that our intervention, a new Framework for introducing Unit Tasks calls attention to the TBLT process and makes students more aware of what and how they are learning so that they can engage in a more meaningful way.

1.5 Document organization

The rest of this document is organized as follows. In Section 2, we describe the school and student make-up as well as characterize the current state of assessment in the classroom to provide additional context to the previously mentioned critical incident. We also describe our intervention at a high level and the tools that we will use to measure the effectiveness of that intervention. In Section 3, we describe our teaching intervention as a new framework for introducing Unit Tasks, and we focus on how the students reacted to these tools and the extent to which they helped us to achieve the objectives of this project. In Section 4, we provide the generic tools along with suggestions on how to implement them in the classroom. Finally, we discuss a series of “next steps” where we suggest how this project might be extended in order to further our goals.

2 Classroom observation

Prior to describing the teaching intervention, it is important that we contextualize the critical incident by providing some additional information about the EOIX, the students in the second-level English classes and the current state of assessment in the school.

2.1 The groups

Throughout our 7-week Practicum, we primarily worked with two Level 2 (CEFR A2) English classes. Both groups are multi-generational (ages 16 to 60+) and have approximately 30 students. The students have diverse backgrounds and motivations for learning English. The younger students are either trying to improve their chances of securing a job or working to complete an official degree or certificate or complementing their university studies. While some of the older students may be studying English for work-related reasons, many are studying for the simple pleasure of learning something new or relearning something previously studied.

Group 1 consists of more older adults (from middle age onwards) and fewer teenagers and millennials. The students’ key strengths are that they are highly motivated and generally have a positive attitude toward learning English. The students have a considerably strong attendance record and work to make the most of each lesson. From time to time, they lack confidence in themselves, but they compensate for this by putting extra effort into classroom tasks; they nearly always complete the homework tasks. Some of the more senior students lack basic IT skills while the younger students are more comfortable with and proficient in using computers. Group 2 includes more young people (ages 16 - 30) than Group 1 which results in a more balanced distribution of ages, and a more balanced classroom in general. The key strengths of these students

are their open attitude toward taking on new challenges as well as their confidence when performing tasks. They are less concerned about making mistakes while speaking and seem to be more comfortable making use of technology in the classroom.

2.2 The school

The EOIX has served as a pioneer and reference for adult language education in Catalunya. Prior to the founding of this school, there were no adult public language schools nearby. This meant that students had to travel to other towns in order to study languages in the public language school system. The establishment of this EOIX has greatly improved access to language learning for adult students in the community. Of particular importance to this TFM is that the central tenet of the EOIX project is a strong dedication to the Task-based Language Teaching (TBTL) methodology.

This EOIX's dedication to TBTL provides important context to this TFM for a variety of distinct reasons. Per the Skehan definition of TBLT that we mentioned at the beginning of this TFM, the student must perform real-world and meaningful tasks using his or her own language. Skehan further stresses that task completion is the priority which means that the assessment is based on the larger (non-linguistic) outcome of the task (Skehan, 2003). This means that students are assessed based on their being able to produce results in a near-real-world situation. As the student has likely neither been exposed to the situation (in the foreign language, English), nor the context of having to complete or solve a problem in the foreign language, we can understand the basis for these students' discomfort.

Taking this concept a step further, the objective of each task is to produce a written and / or spoken text based on a specific genre, and genre represents true social communicative function. We have already mentioned in the previous section that the EOIX does not always teach genre in an explicit way. As it is an adult school, teachers all too often assume that students should already be familiar with common genres such as a formal complaint letter to a company or an Amazon product review (to name a few). However, this is not always the case. Many of the students in these lower levels have been away from formal education for some time and while they may be relatively familiar with a common genre, they may still require a reminder from the teacher to help them recognize it.

At the same time and as we've already mentioned, for students that are used to focus on language and form (meaning exercises, language drilling activities), Task-based learning is messy. In Task-based learning, it is often the case that there is no one correct or incorrect answer to a question. Coursebooks are only used as a reference tool for students, but they are no longer the definitive source of reference. Nowadays, students need to read articles online, watch videos on YouTube, listen to podcasts – all of which can be overwhelming for the level and type of student that we are discussing.

2.3 Taking stock of current assessment practices

We began our investigation into how to increase student confidence in producing language in the face of tasks by reviewing the current EOIX implementation of TBLT with a focus on assessment. In reviewing the “EOIX Programació 2n d'Anglès Curs 2017-2018” we found that each unit consisted of 4-6 sessions which included 1-2 Unit Tasks. Additionally, the students completed a Term Task (or rather series of Tasks)

roughly every 3-4 units. We then examined existing end of Unit / Term Task descriptions as well and their accompanying rubrics.

A clear task description includes: the genre of the text (Is it a written newspaper article or spoken radio advertisement?), cues for the typology (Is the text a narrative, and argumentation meant to convince, etcetera?) and the desired task outcome as well as hints to the type of language that may be employed. While language hints are optional, they can be particularly critical when the teacher wants students to employ newly learned language (expressions, grammar and vocabulary). The accompanying rubric breaks down these task elements (genre, typology and language) individually and explains the degree to which each must be employed to attain a certain level of competency as measured by the task. The larger point is that a clear task description and the rubric, presented at the right point in a didactic sequence or unit can provide students and teachers with a framework for clearer communication and a shared understanding as where they are in their language learning process with respect to the unit (and beyond). Furthermore, having a written task description and rubric may serve to remind students what they have and haven't learned over the course of the unit and over the course of the year.

The purpose of reviewing the existing task descriptions and rubrics used at the EOIX was to understand how expectations with respect to the tasks were currently conveyed to students. First, we confirmed if students were presented with task descriptions and rubrics formally in writing. Next, we analyzed the language and the point systems of the existing rubrics from a student perspective. Our hope was that we would be able to assemble a set of recommendations beginning with the best practices already employed in existing task descriptions and rubrics. Finally, we examined the timing of when the task description and rubric were presented to the student and whether or not the students were allowed to keep printed or digital copies for studying and reflection throughout the course.

As of the beginning of our Didactic Sequence, the students had already performed 7 graded Unit Tasks and 2 graded Term Tasks. While each of the Term Tasks included a detailed and clear Task Description, we found Task Descriptions for only 1 of the 7 Unit Tasks. In the same vein, the teachers had provided written rubrics for the 2 Term Tasks, but only for 1 of the 7 Unit tasks.

TASK BREAKDOWN BY UNIT				
UNITS	UNIT DESCRIPTION	TASK TITLE	TASK DESCRIPTION AVAILABLE	RUBRIC AVAILABLE
Unit 1	My life	"My best..."	No	Description rubric available, but it is unclear if this is the same task
Unit 1	My life	"He's her lobster"	Yes	No rubric available
Unit 2	Let's eat	"Menu"	No	No rubric available
TERM	Term 1 Task	Task 1: Food trends in our city Task 2: Our restaurant: the healthiest in town! Task 3: Places Where People Live the Longest	Yes	Rubric (for writing, understanding and speaking tasks)
Unit 4	Trends	"Susie Style"	No	No rubric available
Unit 3	Mysteries	"Good luck, Bad"	No	No rubric available
Unit 3	Mysteries	Mysteries Part 1 and Part 2 (feedback)	No	Rubric (Self-Assessment)
TERM	Term 2 Task	Task 1: A story of good/bad luck Task 2: Stories that can be watched! Task 3: Modernizing a fairy tale	Yes	Rubric (for writing, understanding and speaking tasks)
Unit 8	Storytelling	Animal Tales	No	No rubric available
		Total <u>written</u> Task description and rubric prior to Didactic Sequence	1 Unit Task / 2 Term Task descriptions	1 Unit Task / 2 Term Task rubrics
Unit 11	Technology	The New New Thing Part 1	Yes	Rubrics provided prior to task
Unit 11	Technology	The New New Thing Part 2	Yes	Rubrics provided prior to task

Table 1. Task Breakdown by Unit

We wondered how and if the absence of written Task Descriptions and Rubrics might contribute to the students' feelings of disorientation because that they could neither see nor follow their progression through the unit and course goals. It is also easy to imagine how students would feel lost while jumping from Unit 4 to Unit 3 to Unit 8 to Unit 11 in their coursebooks. We perceived that some of this disorientation might be remedied by a course syllabus, but we speculated that collection of task descriptions and rubrics would provide a more concrete description of what students were about to learn, were learning and had already learned.

Next, we analyzed existing task descriptions and rubrics from the perspective of the student. To do this, we reviewed the available Term 2 Task descriptions and rubrics in detail.

Task 2: Our restaurant for our city: the healthiest in town!

Watch a video about the unhealthiest restaurant in the world (00:18 to 1:47) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JRJMxZgtlFE>

After this video and based on what you learnt in task 1 about consumers' preferred food characteristics:

Create a Powerpoint presentation in which you will include your restaurant profile: the characteristics of your restaurant, who it is addressed to, what is your menu and you will also create an advertisement for the local radio station → do not forget to include suggestions and pieces of advice.

Do not forget to explain:

- Why the restaurant is the healthiest and the best in town compared to other restaurants and compared to the restaurant from the video.
- What it is like and why it is unusual and unique
- Why people like it and why people should eat there.
- The food you offer, the menu...
- Describe a special dish from the menu, what it tastes like and how it is prepared

The Term 2 Task description includes 2 sub-tasks of different genres, (a) a presentation and (b) an advertisement for a local radio station. At first glance, we can identify several key language elements from the recent units as they are clearly highlighted via visual cues: larger text, bold, underline, check boxes, etc. For example, the task description for sub-task (a), the presentation of the restaurant via PowerPoint, provides a checklist of

Figure 1. Term 2 Task Description

elements that the presentation must include such as language typologies, description and comparison. The task description also suggests some specific language such as “why people should eat [at the restaurant]” and “why [this new restaurant] is unique”. We can also identify the required text typologies in sub-task (b), the commercial in that the description clearly states that students must “include suggestions and pieces and advice”. What is not entirely clear at first glance is how the students will be scored on the task which is information that might be included in a detailed rubric.

Then, we analyzed the accompanying rubrics for these Term Tasks to see how and if these rubrics were being used as an assessment tool. In reviewing the rubrics for consistency, we noted that the rubrics for each activity generally used the same or similar language which focused: task completeness, language richness, language accuracy and pronunciation / intonation.

Speaking - Presentation and Radio Advertisement	★ 2 points	★★ 4 points	★★★ 6 points
Overall impression (communication and task completion)			
Language richness (vocabulary, grammar structures...)			
Language accuracy			
Pronunciation and intonation			

Figure 2. Term 2 Task Rubric

At the same time, we noted that this language may not have clear meaning for students. We, the student-teachers, could easily imagine that our experienced mentors had specific criteria in mind when they referred to “language richness” (related to the use of new and complex vocabulary learned in the units covered) and “language accuracy” (pertaining to appropriate and correct language usage) within the context of the task. However, it would be difficult for students to discern the meaning of these words within the context of the task without additional information. The language “overall impression” and “task completion” is vague at best and can feel quite subjective. Moreover, as the rubric doesn’t specify clear criteria (e.g. vocabulary or new expressions that must be utilized correctly), students may not fully understand why they received 2 points instead of 6 points and perhaps more importantly, how to work to improve their language weak points to attain 6 points in the next Term Task. Additionally, students were not allowed to see the rubric prior to the Term task, nor were they allowed to see and keep the Term Task description for reference throughout the year.

2.4 Analysis: Cooking without a recipe

To give a better sense of how this lack of written task description and rubric may affect the learning process for at least some students, we can explore the idea of cooking a dish without a written recipe. Ask any Catalan 20-something to prepare typical “*truita de patates*” (Potato omelette), and he is not likely going to pull out a recipe card and begin measuring out slices of potato. Instead he is going to more or less know the basic ingredients of eggs, potatoes and onions as well as the general quantities (more eggs than onions) and possibly call his mother or father to remind him of any missing ingredients (salt or that secret addition of cilantro). This Catalan 20-something has already likely observed different family members make many a *truita* over the years, enough so that he has a general idea as to the basic ingredients, the general proportions

and the technique. However, ask any American 20-something to make the perfect *truita de patates*, and she is likely to look up a recipe on the internet (search criteria “best *truita de patates* recipe EVER”) for her very first go. And if she has never tasted a *truita*, she’ll be better prepared to make one if she has had the opportunity to sample one first. That said, we can be certain that both Catalan and American alike can produce delicious *truita de patates*. In other words, cooks that follow a recipe and cooks that do not can both produce *truites* that are equally delicious.

Now let’s bring this analogy back into the English Language learning classroom at the EOIX. It is likely true that when the teacher suggests that the students are going to produce a *truita de patates* (which we can equate to the task), that many of the students have at least an inkling as to what a *truita de patates* is. If we consider the *truita de patates* to represent the general genre of the text, then it is true that at least some of these students can and will be able to deduce the basic ingredients (certain text typologies, grammar) and the possible proportions (critical vocabulary, even specific language) necessary to make an honest attempt at a decent *truita de patates*. That said, it is important that we recognize that not everyone can cook without a recipe, especially not the first time they are making a new dish.

To extend the metaphor further, as we expose students to new genres, the difference between providing the recipe and not providing the recipe potentially becomes more important. If the next time, the teacher asks the students to produce a *truita d’alcaxofes*, the students that have a crystal-clear idea of what makes the perfect *truita de patates* will begin on better footing than those students that don’t. And even those that do not have a crystal-clear idea but that have seen the recipe, might be able to deconstruct the *truita d’alcaxofes* based on what they already know (meaningful learning and the ZPD!). Ideally, we believe that by giving the students a tool that gives students a framework to recognize the genre and text typologies that they have studied previously, they will be able to build upon that knowledge.

2.5 Observation methods

As we have emphasized from the beginning of this TFM, our goal was to help our students face classroom tasks with more confidence while at the same time providing them with a tool for measuring their own progress and or success. Based on our observations in the classroom (critical incident) and our evaluation of the context of the language learning environment of the course, we decided that our students might be best served by addressing the issue of this missing recipe in our teaching intervention.

2.5.1 An innovative framework for Unit Task introduction

For this reason, we decided to use the metaphor of the missing recipe to create a new framework for introducing Unit Tasks in our Didactic Sequence. Instead of introducing the Unit Task near the end of the DS, we would describe it at a high level from the first or second session. The idea was to plant the seed in the students that “by the end of the Unit, they will be able to...” as a means of motivating them. After introducing several Unit Task-relevant vocabulary and grammar concepts, we would show or provide an example of the Unit Task genre. Next, we would work with the students to deconstruct the Task into its most basic and critical elements and come up with a basic “recipe” for the task. Then we would work together to define specific language elements as well as other targets that should be included as a part of the task. Finally, we worked together to define detailed metrics to ensure that students had no question regarding how they

would be evaluated. We referred to this activity as “How to get an A+”, and we used the resulting rubric for a peer evaluation and for grading the students. We later went back to the students to see what they remembered as key learnings from the unit in a reflective survey which we refer to as a “reflection-aire”.

2.5.2 The Recipe for the perfect *truita* and the perfect task

Although we knew that the first part of the framework would be to introduce the task itself and the final part of the framework would include detailed criteria in the form of the rubric, we needed an intermediary step or steps to bridge the gap. We call this intermediary step the Recipe.

The idea for the Recipe was inspired by an activity we saw in a first-year English class. The focus of the unit was food, and the teacher successfully elicited the key elements of a Unit Task which was, in fact, a real recipe - a video recipe. First, the teacher showed the class an example of a video recipe in order to familiarize the students with the genre. Next, he asked the students to work in groups to create a simple recipe for *truita*. Then, as a class, he asked each group to provide the various elements of the recipe, using vocabulary to trigger a logical order (“First we need to know the...”). As each group identified their respective element(s), the teacher wrote them down in a mind map on the board. The students initially provided the most obvious elements that make up the recipe genre (ingredients, instructions), but once the students saw the mind map, they eventually “caught on” and provided much more complex elements of the recipe including number of servings, cooking utensils, the use of commands, hints, etcetera. The teacher then extended the mind map to include additional relevant language from the unit. By the end of the task, the students had a unique visual representation of the Unit Task in the form of a mind map. At the end of this carefully guided activity, the teacher provided the students with a clear task description in which each of the elements discussed appeared, so as to remind the students of what they were studying and thus what they needed to produce in order to complete the task.

From the moment we first observed this activity, we wondered how we might apply the general idea to the two Unit Tasks that we were preparing for our Didactic Sequence. Despite the fact that neither of the tasks was a recipe, we thought that we could employ the recipe as a metaphor for breaking the Unit Tasks down into the key “ingredients”. In consulting a bit further with the teacher, we came up with following two tools. First, we would use the visual concept of the Recipe to help students to break down or deconstruct the task into the most essential elements of genre and language. Then, we would break down the recipe even further, adding target metrics for critical grammar and vocabulary and provide a “How to get an A+ (perfect score)” Rubric that would not only help students to prepare for the task but would also help teachers to grade the task.

From this point forward when we refer to the framework, we are referring to the following set of tools:

1. Unit Task Description
2. Unit Task Recipe
3. Unit Task Rubric Checklist
4. Unit Task Rubric (corrected by their teacher)
5. Unit Reflection-aire

In truth, we originally conceived of the idea 5. Unit Reflection-aire as an Observation Tool in and of itself. The idea was to employ periodic group reflection (each week or fortnight) on the students’ perception of their own learning curve to see if / how we might be able to change that perception over time. However, during the intervention process, we discovered that this tool should be integrated as a part of the framework for maximum impact which we discuss in the sections to follow.

Once we implemented the framework, we conducted a short survey to see if the framework had a positive or negative effect on student confidence coming into the task. We discuss the implementation and corresponding results of this survey in Section 3.2.

3 Teaching intervention and outcome

3.1 What we did: Introducing the Framework, the Recipe and the Rubric

At the highest level, our intervention consisted of implementing an innovative framework (and related tools) for introducing Unit Tasks in the context of our Didactic Sequence or DS. To better understand how we introduced the framework, we must first put this DS into context. The DS consisted of 6 sessions, each of which was approximately 2 hours long, that loosely followed the book unit (Unit 11) which focused on the topic of Technology. Over the course of the DS, students were required to complete 2 Unit Tasks that were based on an initial activity to produce a gadget out of recycled materials that would help them simplify or solve a problem in their everyday lives. The fact that there were 2 Unit Tasks meant that we could implement the framework twice (once for each task) and have the unique opportunity to gauge student reactions and possibly make minor adjustments for the second task.

For the Unit Task 1 (written), students created a 3-4 slide Elevator pitch presentation (persuasive presentation used to spark interest in an idea) for investors. The communicative purpose of the task was to describe, compare and persuade the audience that a) their gadget solved an important problem, and that b) the investors should invest in their idea. For the Unit Task 2, students created and recorded a 1-minute television commercial for their product for the public-at-large. Both tasks were to be performed in groups of 3-4 students. The strength of using these two similar genres in a single DS is that they allowed the students to employ the various language elements that were covered throughout the sequence more than once with only slight modification which would further solidify their understanding of these elements.

Each session in the sequence consisted of student-centered “activities” that addressed the different DS Goals using a variety of language content. This content was interspersed with the preparatory steps for the Unit Tasks as shown in the table below.

SESSION	“ACTIVITIES” and DS GOALS	CONTENT and LANGUAGE	UNIT TASK FRAMEWORK
Session 1	“My life in technology”- Personal introductions, “My Precious Object” - Describing objects and Comparing similar objects	Scaffolding: <i>It's made of / from</i> (materials: wood, plastic), <i>It's used for...-ing</i> , <i>Size: It is bigger than... / It is as big as a...</i>	Unit Objectives - Concise description of Unit Tasks 1 and 2

Session 2	“BeFit” - Describing objects and -able vocabulary, “Kids react to old computers” - computer vocabulary, “The perfect presidential present” – Comparing objects	Vocabulary: Computer / mouse / monitor / etc., Vocabulary: <i>affordable / manageable / reliable / remarkable / etc.</i>	Unit Task 1 - Initial (concise) Description
Session 3	“Pit-a-pocket Pitch Presentation” - Describing objects, Comparing similar objects	Vocabulary: <i>affordable / manageable / reliable / remarkable / etc.</i>	Unit Task 1 - Example of Task, Deconstructing and reconstructing the Recipe
Session 4	“I can’t live without my smart phone” - Internet / Smart Phone vocabulary, “I can live without my smartphone” - Describing habits in the past, Counterargument	<i>Used to, People say... but actually</i> , Vocabulary: <i>download videos / share photos on Instagram / post on Facebook</i>	Unit Task 1 - Using the rubric for peer evaluation
Session 5	“Fedex and the Shrink ray” - Describing objects and Comparing similar objects (Call to action)	Commands as a call to action: <i>Buy it / Use it / Try it</i>	Unit Task 2 - Example of Task, Deconstructing and reconstructing the Recipe
Session 6	“Command hanging strips” - Describing objects, Commands (Call to action)	<i>Buy it / Visit our webpage, Commercial</i>	Unit Task 1 - Using the rubric self-evaluation
Post			Teacher corrections and Reflection via the Reflection-aire

Table 2. Didactic Sequence Summary and Unit Task Framework

As this TFM focuses primarily on Unit Tasks and how they are introduced via the framework, we will shift our focus away from contents of the sequence to see specifically how and when we implemented the framework and associated tools in detail.

Session 1 – Introducing the Unit and objectives: In the first session, we introduced the topic and the objectives of the unit, focusing on what students would be able to do at the end of the unit: “By the end of the unit, you will be able to describe an object and compare it with a similar object, etc....”. We also told students that they would be creating and selling a gadget to solve a problem in their everyday lives to get them thinking about the gadget that they would make and tied this back to the objectives of the unit.

Session 2 – Describing Unit Task 1: In Session 2, we introduced the Unit Tasks 1 and 2 verbally. We told students that they would need to work together to create a gadget to solve a problem in their daily lives and that they would have to pitch their gadget to investors and eventually sell their gadget to the public. The idea was to give the students an idea of the general direction of the sequence without overwhelming them with too much initial information.

Session 3 – Learning by example, deconstructing and rebuilding the Recipe together:

In the third session of the sequence, we told students that they would be creating an elevator pitch presentation and wrote the name of this complex genre on the board. We began by defining what is an “Investor” using simple language: “Investors fund [or give money to] good ideas”. Next, we presented the genre as “a short persuasive presentation used to generate interest in an idea [your gadget]”. As the genre was difficult, we tried to use cognates in the description when possible to ensure that the students would understand the more complex words which we wrote them on the board. We also asked about the significance of the word, “Elevator”, pointing out that the presentation should be short, “It should last no longer than an elevator ride (45 seconds).” Next, we had them read a short Unit Task 1 description out loud from the digital board.

The graphic is a rectangular box with a white top section and a dark grey bottom section. The top section contains three logos: 'Angel Investment Network' (a blue and yellow circle), '22@ network bcn' (with '22@' in purple and 'network bcn' in red, and 'districte d'innovació' written vertically in red), and 'Ajuntament de Barcelona' (a red square with a white crown and shield). The bottom section is split diagonally. The left side is dark grey and contains white text: 'An Investor is working with 22@ to fund local technology projects in Barcelona, Hospitalet and Cornellà. They are holding a competition to decide which products to fund. Produce a **3-4 slide elevator pitch presentation (200 words)** that *describes and promotes* your gadget to submit to the competition.' The right side is light grey and contains the text 'Unit Task 1: The New New Thing' in bold black font.

Figure 3. Unit Task 1 Description

At this point, we provided the students with an example of the genre, a sample elevator pitch presentation. We had a difficult time finding an example presentation online that was not full of investor jargon, so we created our own example. We made the presentation theatrical and fun to get the students’ undivided attention. In the sample presentation, we also modeled the language that we expected students to use. It is important to note that we didn’t provide the example to the students in digital or paper form. Our goal wasn’t for students to copy the example, so much as to begin to assimilate their understanding of the genre.

The Solution: Pit-a-Pocket is a **new and convenient** way to carry your phone while running.

- ▶ It has 2 adjustable straps, 2 protective cups and a durable pocket for your phone. The pocket has a window so that you can access the button quickly. The lid opens and closes easily.
- ▶ It is made from recycled plastic and cardboard.
- ▶ It is **more comfortable and reliable** than a running armband. It won't fall down.
- ▶ Some people may think that this product is expensive but actually, **it is as affordable as a running armband**.
- ▶ I will sell it for only 29.99€.

Figure 4. Unit Task 1 Example

After we presented the sample elevator pitch presentation, we worked as a class to define the key elements that would be required for the task. The objective was to deconstruct the task into the distinct elements, so that we could later create a clear rubric. As the students called out their ideas, we wrote them on the board in a mind map. We focused first and foremost on the 3-4 key elements of the genre – the fact that the presentation had to describe the problem (Problem) that the gadget was designed to solve and how it was in fact the solution to that problem (Solution). We then added the importance of Market Data as the final defining criteria of the genre (a pitch to Investors) which would differentiate this pitch from publicity, meaning print advertisements and commercials.

Next, we asked the students to suggest the language that they felt should be a part of the Unit Task 1 based on what they had studied in previous sessions. They provided vocabulary (-able adjectives such as “affordable”) as well as grammar-related language (as ... as for comparatives). We added that language to the mind map on the board and added the names of the text typologies (Describe, Compare, Convince, Counterargue). To wrap up the activity, we summarized the ingredients in a graphic that we would reference throughout the remainder of the sequence, shown below.

Figure 5. Unit Task 1 Recipe

We also provided a detailed written Unit Task 1 Description. Having discussed the Recipe for the perfect task in detail, we projected our graphic on the digital board and the mind map on the whiteboard, and we let the students work on their presentations.

Session 4 – Using Rubrics as tools for self and peer evaluation: We began this session by having students elicit the Recipe from the previous day’s activity and mind map. We had transformed this detailed list into a detailed rubric with specific and measurable criteria that was based on our own requirements in combination with student input from the previous session.

Unit Task 1: Elevator Pitch Presentation - HOW TO GET AN A+ RUBRIC						
CRITERIA	DESCRIPTION		EXPERT (EXCELLENT)		INTERMEDIATE (ACCEPTABLE)	NOVICE (NEEDS IMPROVEMENT)
1. Genre Ingredients	The presentation includes all of the ingredients: Problem, Solution, Market Data, Catchy Name and Image.	4	All ingredients	3	3 ingredients	2 2 ingredients
2. Description	The students describe 6 or more qualities of the gadget including: It is made from, It is used for, It is (shape, color, etc.), It has (features or parts).	6	6+ qualities	4	4-5 qualities	2 2-3 qualities
3. Description	The students describe the gadget using 4-able adjectives: affordable, manageable, etc.	4	4+ -able adjectives	3	3 -able adjectives	2 2 -able adjectives
4. Comparatives / Counterargument	The students compare their gadget with other solutions using the 2 comparatives: It is more... than, It is as... as and make 1 counterargument: People think..., but actually...	3	2 comparatives AND 1 counterargument	2	1 comparative AND 1 counterargument or 2 comparatives	1 1 comparative OR 1 counterargument
5. Accuracy	The verbs are always correctly conjugated	3	always (0 errors)	2	most of the time (1-2 errors)	1 rarely (3-4 errors)
TOTAL		20		14		8
20		100%		70%		40%

Figure 6. Unit Task 1 Rubric

However, instead of providing the rubric to the students, we instead modified the rubric to resemble a checklist. We asked each group to use the checklist to help another peer group to improve their presentation as shown in the example below.

The PERFECT Presentation: How to get an A+				
CRITERIA	DESCRIPTION	EXPERT (EXCELLENT)	✓	NOTES
1. Genre Ingredients	The presentation includes all of the ingredients : <i>Problem, Solution, Market Data, Catchy Name and Image</i>	4 All ingredients	✓	
2. Description	The students describe 6 or more qualities of the gadget. (<i>It is made of... It has [feature], It is used for...</i>)	6 6+ qualities	✓	
3. Description	The students describe the gadget using 4-able adjectives : <i>affordable, reliable...</i>	4 4+ -able adjectives		Needs 2 more
4. Comparatives / Counterargument	The students compare their gadget with other solutions using the 2 comparatives (<i>It is more... than, It is as... as</i>) and make 1 counterargument . (<i>People say... but actually...</i>)	2 comparatives AND 1 counterargument		Check counterargument
5. Accuracy	The verbs are always correctly conjugated	3 always (0 errors)		She are → is
TOTAL		20	100%	

Figure 7. Unit Task 1 Checklist

The rubric checklist provided “everything” that we perceived to be important for their successful completion of the task, including hints regarding the specific language that they should use. At the end of Session 4, we assigned the remaining work on the pitch presentation as homework, so that we could move on to Unit Task 2.

Session 5 - Learning by example, deconstructing and rebuilding the Recipe: In Session 5, we focused on the Unit Task 2, the commercial. As we had done with the previous Unit Task 1, we began by providing students with an example commercial.

Commercials and Call to Action

- Watch the [commercial](#).

BUY IT NOW

VISIT OUR WEBSITE
shutterstock

try it now!

Call Us Now!
888-888-0001

Small 3M Command Strips
Picture Hanging Strips
Comes off cleanly
No nail holes
Repositions for easy leveling
450 g / 1.5 lb
172020

Figure 8. Unit Task 2 Example

We then worked together as a class to brainstorm the elements that make up the genre, the commercial. As commercials are generally a well-known genre, it did not take the students long to fill out the various elements of the Recipe. We had chosen the Commercial to follow the Elevator Pitch Presentation as these genres have many elements in common (discussion about a problem that you wish to solve, etc.). This provided us with the opportunity to reinforce the language and the learning that the students had already used in Unit Task 1, because they could use this language again in Unit Task 2. As we did with Unit Task 1, we created a mind map on the board and then provided the graphic to represent the various elements to the students.

Figure 9. Unit Task 2 Recipe

Session 6 – Using Rubrics as tools for self-evaluation: We followed a similar procedure in Session 6 as we did in Session 4. We began this session by having students elicit the Recipe from the previous day’s activity and mind map. We then provided the students with a detailed Unit Task 2 description and another rubric checklist with specific and measurable criteria for the task. This time, we did not include specific language hints on the rubric-based checklist as we wanted to see if students could deduce this aspect for themselves. Moreover, instead of having students review the work of others, we provided them the rubric to evaluate their own group’s work. We reminded the students that we would use this same rubric to grade their work, and that if they could meet the requirements, they would indeed get an A+.

The PERFECT Commercial: How to get an A+

CRITERIA	DESCRIPTION		EXPERT (EXCELLENT)	✓	NOTES
1. Genre Ingredients	The presentation includes all of the ingredients : Problem, Solution, Information (where, how, how much), Call to Action.	4	All ingredients	✓	
2. Description	The students describe 6 or more qualities of the gadget.	6	6+ qualities	✓	
3. Description	The students describe the gadget using 4-able adjectives .	4	4+ -able adjectives	✓	
4. Comparatives / Counterargument	The students compare their gadget with other solutions using the 2 comparatives and make 1 counterargument .	3	2 comparatives AND 1 counterargument	✓	
5. Pronunciation	The pronunciation is always perfect.	3	always (0 errors)		
TOTAL		20	100%		

Figure 10. Unit Task 2 Checklist

Post-DS – Using Rubrics for correcting: It is important to note that we used the same rubric that we had provided to the students (in checklist form) to correct and score Unit Task 1 and Unit Task 2. For Unit Task 1, we provided in-line corrections on the presentation in addition to a rubric slide. The rubric slide allowed students to see in which areas they excelled as well as suggested areas of improvement. The idea was to provide this to the student in digital or paper form, although we did not see if the teachers of the EOIX actually gave this back to the students due to the fact that our DS ended.

Reflection-aire – A look back on what we did to remind us of what we know: Once we had completed the two Unit Tasks, we provided the students with a questionnaire for reflecting (“Reflection-aire) on what they had learned during the 6 sessions of the DS. This Reflection-aire proposed a series of communicative objectives in their native / second language. We included between 1 and 3 “false” objectives and instructed the students to confirm whether or not an objective was (true) or was not (false) a part of the DS.

For each item that was true (veritat), we then asked students to provide “evidence” of having worked on the listed communicative objective by naming or describing an activity, a section from the book that we had covered in class or some aspect of the Unit Tasks that we had covered over the course of the DS. Our goals see to what extent students could identify their own key learnings from the unit. We performed the Reflection-aire for the DS (Unit 11) as a class and include the completed survey below:

<p>UNIT 11: Technology</p>	<p>Al final d'aquesta unitat, farrem un "gadget" de reciclatge, redactarem una presentació per a inversors, crearem un anunci i el representarem.</p> <p><i>At the end of this unit we will have made a gadget; we will then create a presentation about this gadget for investors and make a commercial.</i></p> <p>Per això aprendrem a:</p> <p><i>To be able to do this, we will learn to:</i></p>	<p>EVIDÈNCIA: Llibre (pp.), Activitats, Lectures, Lenguatge</p> <p>EVIDENCE: Book, Activites, Readings, Language</p> <p>(Answers provided by students)</p>	<p>Veritat / Fals</p> <p><i>TRUE or FALSE</i></p> <p>(Answers provided by students)</p>
<p>11.1</p>	<p>Descriure un objecte</p> <p><i>To describe an object.</i></p>	<p>"Mind map", <i>It's made of / from (materials: wood, plastic), Color, Size: It's bigger than..., Shape: cylindrical, It's used for...-ing, It's used to..., It is bigger than, "Kids react to computers", "Elevator Pitch Presentation"</i></p>	<p>V</p>
<p>11.2</p>	<p>Plantejar hipotesis sobre la tecnologia del future</p> <p><i>Make hypotheses about the technology of the future</i></p>	<p>NO</p>	<p>F</p>
<p>11.3</p>	<p>Explicar rutines passats i com han canviat</p> <p><i>To explain past routines and how they have changed</i></p>	<p>"I can live without my mobile phone": <i>I used to take photos with my camera. I used to watch movies at the theatre.</i></p>	<p>V</p>
<p>11.4</p>	<p>Comparar ítems similar</p> <p>To compare similar items</p>	<p><i>as big as, "Trump birthday present"</i></p>	<p>V</p>
<p>11.5</p>	<p>Lèxic de la descripció (adjectius...)</p> <p><i>Descriptive words (adjectives, etc.)</i></p>	<p><i>easy-to-use, manageable, available, affordable, comfortable, fashionable, catchy, boxy from Kids react to computers", "Elevator pitch presentation"</i></p>	<p>V</p>
<p>11.6</p>	<p>Text persuasiu / argumentatiu</p> <p><i>Persuasive / argumentative text</i></p>	<p>"Commercial", Counterargument: <i>People say it's difficult to use, but actually it's manageable. Call to action: buy it, use it, try it, visit our website, Comparatiu: it's better than...it's more affordable than</i></p>	<p>V</p>

Table 3. Unit 11 Reflection-aire

While we initially envisioned this task as a kind of observation tool that existed outside of the framework, we have included it here because we discovered the inherent value

of having the students perform this kind of reflection just after completing the unit while performing the activity itself. We will discuss this more in the sections that follow.

3.2 Results – What we saw and what it means

As mentioned in previous sections, our goal was to provide our students with tools that would help them to face classroom tasks with more confidence as well as to provide them with a sense of progress and accomplishment. In order to better understand the extent to which this framework and the accompanying tools the Recipe (How to get an A+), the Rubric and the Reflection-aire provided the students with this confidence, we conducted a short survey after the completion of DS and evaluated the output from the Reflection-aire.

The survey was not obligatory; it was neither given as a class assignment, nor as a homework item. Despite this fact, we had a relatively high response rate for Group 1 at 81% and a nearly perfect response rate for Group 2 for a total response rate of 89%. We calculated the response rate by comparing the number of responses that we received with the number of “active students” in each group. We define “active students” as students that had completed 75% of all Unit Tasks (including the combined task of our Didactic Sequence, Unit 11) as well as both of the Term Tasks.

SURVEY RESPONSES	RESPONSES	ACTIVE STUDENTS	RESPONSE RATE
Group 1	21	26	81%
Group 2	30	31	97%
Total Students	51	57	89%

Table 4. Survey Response Overview

It is important to note that the survey was sent to the students before they had received their grades for the combined Unit Task from the DS. Had we given the survey after the students had received their grades, we would be concerned that their grades might influence the way that they felt about the tools. For example, had the student grade been higher than the student had expected, that same student may have felt biased toward a more positive response. Likewise, had the student grade been lower than the student had expected, the student may have felt biased toward a more negative response.

3.2.1 Baseline feelings about class pacing fit expectations

One of the first objectives of the survey was to try to gauge to what extent students could or could not follow the pace of the class as they suggested at least anecdotally on task day. To do this, we asked students to tell us how often they felt that they could not keep up with the pace of the class: Never, Rarely, Often, Very often or Always.

Figure 11: Question (2) I think that the rhythm of the class is too fast for me: Never, Rarely, Often, Very often, Always

From the survey, we learned that that more than one quarter of the students never have problems keeping up with the pace of the class and that the majority of the students only have problems keeping up with the pace of the class from time to time. We also found that nearly a quarter of the students were unable to follow the rhythm of the class on a regular basis. We had anticipated that this number could be higher due to our observations and the critical incident, but the survey shows the class to fit a relatively standard distribution.

3.2.2 Students feel more confident coming into a task when they know what is expected of them

Next, we asked the students to reflect on the framework for introducing tasks. As we have mentioned throughout this TFM, we suspected that students would feel more confident knowing exactly what was expected of them; however, we didn't know to what extent our results would bear that theory out. Moreover, we were unsure if some students would feel more pressure in having a list of expectations prior to their task.

Figure 12. Question (3) If I compare the technology unit tasks with previous tasks, knowing how to get an A+ made me feel: Much more confident, more confident, the same, less confident, much less confident

The results show that 62.7% of students felt more confident entering into the Unit Task for our DS over previous units and that nearly 20% of students felt much more confident having been given the Recipe (How to get an A+) and Rubric. All told, more than 80% of students believed that our tools impacted their attitude going into the tasks in a positive way. Perhaps what is even more interesting is while the remaining 20% of students responded that the tools had no effect on their attitude going into the task, 0% of students responded that our tools impacted their experience in a negative way.

Knowing that more than 80% of students believe that having the Recipe (How to get an A+) and Rubric helped them to feel more confident entering into the Unit Tasks for our DS, we suspected that the same or nearly the same percentage of students would feel that the framework would help them on the subsequent Unit Tasks.

Figure 13. Question (4) Would it help you to know the recipe and rubric for the next unit task? Yes, It doesn't matter, No

However, we saw that number increase by nearly 15%. We must be cautious when drawing conclusions, but this increase might suggest that students didn't understand the value of the Recipe and the Rubric until they used them in the task which in turn increased their confidence in the tools. If we look at the data from another perspective, we see that no student answered "No". We might deduce that while some students don't feel strongly that the tools will have a strong positive impact, at the very least they also don't feel that the tools will have a strong negative impact. In other words, they are open to the possibility that these tools may improve their experience.

3.2.3 Students can reflect better on their own learning (growth) when they reflect on what and how much they are learning

As we explained in the previous section, we asked students to briefly reflect on the language that they believed that they had learned throughout our 12-hour DS. Additionally, we asked the students to review the communicative goals for all units prior to our Didactic Sequence. We completed the survey for our DS together, but we assigned the remaining (other) units to groups of 3 and 4 with each group completing the survey for a different unit. As we explained in the previous section, each survey sheet proposed a list of "objectives" for each unit; however, we also included "fake" or false objectives from each unit. We allowed each group to work together to provide

“Evidence” in the form of language, page numbers and activity descriptions for each true objective while at the same time leaving any fake or false objectives blank.

We then coded for all of the language that students remembered as we felt that the top objective of the class was the language. For each unit, we identified how many expressions, nouns, verbs, adjectives and adverbs the students could remember and counted them. The results are provided in the table below:

ORDER	UNIT	Expressions	Nouns	Adjectives	Adverbs	Verb	Non-book Activity	TOTAL
1	Unit 1 (My Life)	16	8	0	1	2	18	45
2	Unit 2 (Let's Eat!)	17	10	7	0	0	1	35
3	Unit 4 (Trends)	8	0	10	4	12	3	37
4	Unit 3 (Mysteries)	0	0	0	0	8	7	15
5	Unit 8 (Storytelling)	7	0	3	1	0	16	27
6	Unit 11 (Technology)	11	10	21	0	6	10	58
	TOTAL	59	28	41	6	28	55	217

Table 5. Reflection-aire Coded Results by Unit

The table itself is a testament that learning is taking place, and that perhaps the students just need to be reminded of this from time to time. Also, the fact that students could identify more of their learnings for the most recent DS unit, unit 11, is an interesting data point. This could be simply because we forget over time, or it could also be attributed to the fact that we completed the first survey as a class. Regardless of the reason, the outcome suggests that perhaps an appropriate time to reflect on a student’s key learnings from a unit is, in fact, just after completion of the unit.

In addition to asking students to reflect on the framework and tools, we also asked students to quantify how much they had learned in terms of new vocabulary during the DS. This survey question was by no means exhaustive in that it merely asked for the number of words that students had learned rather than specifying part of speech versus expressions or grammar-related vocabulary. The motivation behind the question was to see how much students perceived to have learned via the DS and after having completed the Reflection-aire.

Figure 14. Question (1) Doing the Technology Unit Tasks, I learned: More than 10 new words, 7-9 new words, 4-6 new words, 1-3 new words, 0 new words (Words includes all parts of speech)

We were pleased to see that nearly 73% of students felt that they had increased their vocabulary by more than 10 words. We believe that this positive response can be attributed, at least in part, to the fact that students filled out the Reflection-aire prior to completing this survey, so they had key learning present in their minds.

4 Conclusions and future directions

In the previous sections, we've explained that our intervention consisted of implementing an innovative framework (and related tools) for introducing Unit Tasks with the larger goal of instilling students with more confidence in the face of tasks and providing these students with a way to measure their own progress and or success. We've also provided evidence (via our results) that this framework can positively impact the student experience in the classroom. Based on this experience and subsequent results, we provide the recommendations that follow.

4.1 The framework: a predictable paradigm within the classroom

We believe that creating a predictable sequence of classroom activities can provide students with more confidence in the classroom. We realized this when we were introducing the second Unit Task of the DS. We had suspected that there was value in providing a framework from the outset of the DS, but we noticed that students appreciated “knowing what came next” in the repetition of this framework for Unit Task 2 because some of this commented on this to us directly. Specifically, students didn't quite believe that we were providing them with a kind of cheat sheet or “*chuleta*” for succeeding on the task, particularly the first time that we did it. However, by the second time that used the framework to introduce the task, we had set an expectation as to how we would present the future tasks as well as put emphasis on how we would accompany the students in understanding and succeeding on the task. Some of these students recognized this and took clear advantage of the tools provided to them.

For those wishing to implement the framework, we offer this breakdown into steps:

STEP	UNIT TASK FRAMEWORK
1	Provide Unit Objectives and initial (concise) Task Description (not in writing)
2	Show Unit Task Example, Build the Recipe, Provide Detailed <u>Unit Task Description</u> and <u>Recipe for the Perfect Unit Task</u> .
3	Provide <u>Unit Task Rubric Checklist</u> for peer evaluation or self-evaluation
4	Provide corrected <u>Unit Task Rubric</u> (and Unit Task)
5	Lead individual or group reflection via <u>Reflection-aire</u>
DOCUMENTS that student will have at the end of the process: Unit Task Description, Recipe, Unit Task Rubric Checklist, Unit Task Rubric, Reflection-aire.	

Table 6. Unit Task Framework (Tool)

We recognize an important limitation of this TFM in that we could only look at implementation of the framework for two Unit Tasks. We would have liked to have

been able to evaluate the success of the framework implemented on a regular basis (for all Units) and suggest that this might be an interesting direction for this work.

4.2 A Recipe for success

As we have discussed previously in the document, in TBLT, we are often teaching genre as much as we are teaching language.

For those wishing to try to implement the Recipe in their classroom, we offer the following generic format:

Figure 15. Unit Task Recipe (Tool)

Based on our student responses, we believe that the Recipe is a simple but effective tool for eliciting and reminding students of the key elements of the genre at least in the lower level English classes where genres are simplified.

4.3 Building an A+ Rubric

In reviewing the different aspects of the framework, we believe that the most difficult tool to produce is the rubric. The current EOIX rubrics (see Figure 2) served mainly as a correction tool for teachers, but we wanted to use the rubric to establish a common vocabulary between teacher and student that would reflect the student's progress. What we attempted to do was to combine some of the criteria that was present in the teacher's initial rubrics, describing task completeness, language richness and language accuracy. However, we were defining student success in a much more concrete fashion.

Looking at the A+ Rubric (see Figure 6) instead of the imprecise term, "completeness", we were reminding the students that their presentation needed to include all of the key elements for the genre in "1. Genre Ingredients". In terms of language richness, we provided several aspects of "2. / 3. Description" as well as comparison and argument (4), which focused on both the grammatical points and the vocabulary linked to the text typology. We added "5. Accuracy" based on the suggestion of the teacher which focused on verb conjugation as an area of much needed area of improvement; however,

instead of mentioning general accuracy, we suggested that the focal point would be verbs so that students knew where they needed to pay the most attention.

Additionally, the organization of the rubric from lowest score to highest score gives the impression that students may not be expected to do well on the exam. For this reason, we tried to shift the emphasis of the rubric to excellence by initially providing a checklist that focused only on the A+ scoring to the students. Moreover, we changed the order to the rubric to show the target grade (A+) closest to the criterion to bring student focus toward doing the best work possible.

While this paper largely deals with the sentiments of students, it is important to point out that some aspects of our rubrics were (and are still) less than ideal.

For example, while employing the Unit Task 1 Rubric, we noticed that we did not have a way of scoring excellent organization and professionalism of the presentation. In both Unit Tasks 1 and 2, we noticed that some rubric criterion overlapped which made them more difficult to grade. For example, if a student included -able adjectives in their description of the gadget, it was unclear as to whether that should count as part of the description, usage of key vocabulary or both. Moreover, for Unit Task 2, we realized that we did not specify to what extent the production should be rehearsed or read.

We have worked to address the known shortcomings in a generic rubric that we present here:

Table 7. How to get an A+ Rubric (Tool)

HOW TO GET AN A+ RUBRIC					
GENERAL CRITERIA	QUESTIONS TO DETERMINE SPECIFIC CRITERIA	TASK TYPE	SAMPLE SPECIFIC CRITERIA (Based on TASK: The New New Thing)		EXPERT (EXCELLENT)
Completeness	Basic Genre Ingredients: What are the bare minimum requirements (including the 3-4 genre elements) for your students to "complete the activity"?	Oral Task / Written Task	The presentation includes all of the ingredients: Problem, Solution, Market Data, Catchy Name and Image.	4	All ingredients
Completeness, Richness	Text Typology: Is there specific grammar (related to a text typology or not) that you want to include in the task?	Oral Task / Written Task	The student describes 4 or more qualities of the gadget including: It is made from, It is used for, It is (shape, color, etc.), It has (features or parts).	4	4+ qualities
Completeness, Richness	Text Typology: Is there specific grammar (related to a text typology or not) that you want to include in the task?	Oral Task / Written Task	The student compares his or her gadget with other solutions using the 2 comparatives: It is more... than, It is as... as and make 1 counterargument: People think..., but actually...	3	2 comparatives AND 1 counterargument
Richness	Theme: Is there specific vocabulary (adjectives, nouns, verbs, adverbs) that you want included in the task?	Oral Task / Written Task	The student describes the gadget using 4-able adjectives: affordable, manageable, etc.	4	4+ -able adjectives
Accuracy	Accuracy: Is there a weakness that should be a focal point for the students [all students / the specific student]?	Written Task	The verbs are always conjugated correctly.	3	always (0 errors)
		Oral Task	The -able adjectives are always pronounced correctly.		always (0 errors)
Other	Is the presentation or essay of professional quality? Do the students need to include an image?	Written Task	The students have made good use of a presentation template and images. The presentation is well-structured and easy-to-follow.	2	The presentation is well structured AND makes good use of template and / or images.
Other	Presentation: Is it important that the students produce something rehearsed? Can the students read? OR Is it more important that they be spontaneous? Must they record the video from start to finish without stopping and / or without post-production?	Oral Task	The students must produce natural speech in the video / recording. This means that they do not memorize or read from a script.		The students present using natural speech (not memorized, no reading) AND the students do not stop the video and start again.
	TOTAL	20		20	100%

4.4 Creating the Personal Portfolio

As we mentioned previously, students had a challenging time understanding their own progress because they do not have evidence of this progress in a form that they are used to. For this reason, we suggest providing students with a written / printed reminder of their progress, much like having a book. To do this, we recommend having students archive their progress in the same way for each unit, building the course syllabus as they progress through the term. The advantage of this exercise is that students would not be developing a generic course syllabus but rather they would be building a personal portfolio that describes their strengths, weaknesses, points for improvement and beyond. For each DS (represented by a unit), the student would archive the following documents in the Personal Portfolio:

1. Unit Task Description
2. Unit Task Recipe

3. Unit Task Rubric Checklist
4. Unit Task Rubric (corrected by their teacher)
5. Unit Reflection-aire

In providing the students with clear feedback, we are essentially providing them with a way forward when knowledge is cumulative.

4.5 Future directions

This TFM represents the pilot implementation of a new framework and associated tools for introducing tasks, mainly Unit Tasks in the context of the EOIX. The project was limited to the 6 DS sessions for 2 classes (approximately 60 students) that covered one unit of the 9-10 units covered over the course of a year. While these initial results are promising, they are somewhat inconclusive from a research perspective due to a small sample size.

That said, there are several ways that we envision this work being further developed. First, we can imagine the framework being extended to every or nearly every Unit Task over the course of an entire year. We would be interested in collecting more extensive data from students (perhaps at a larger scale) to see if our theory continues to yield the same result. We would be particularly interested in look at the Reflection-aire's impact over time. During an extended follow-up study, we could also study how the framework impacts teachers, their planning and their corrections, for better or for worse. Second, we might consider extending this approach to languages other than English. There is considerable opportunity for collaboration across languages at a school such as the EOIX and we are aware that there is considerable interest and expertise in the other language departments. Finally, we would also like to explore adapting rubric criteria to the specific needs of individual students in an effort to understand to what extent we can provide a personalized education experience.

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7 Annexes

The following tools are provided as original templates and documents so that they may be easily adapted according to teacher needs.

They are available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18656992>.

7.1 Sample Recipes and Rubric Checklists

7.2 Sample Unit Task Descriptions

7.3 How to Get an A+ Rubric (General)